

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

California State University, Fullerton
California State University, Los Angeles
Kaiser Permanente School of Anesthesia

MOBILE TEAMS – REACHING HIGH-RISK COMMUNITIES WITH VACCINATION AND
TESTING

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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ABSTRACT

As COVID-19 became a global pandemic in 2020, Los Angeles County (LAC) residents were affected. Those who experienced negative social determinants of health were affected disproportionately in disease rate and severity. These individuals were also less vaccinated for COVID-19. In response to disparities in vaccination, the Los Angeles County Department of Public Health created the Mobile Vaccine Team (MVT) in 2021. The MVT provides vaccines for COVID-19 and other illnesses, going to sites throughout LAC. LAC continued to experience high rates of communicable disease (CD), including sexually transmitted infections, with increases in marginalized groups. This project primarily aimed to evaluate the impact of the MVT in vaccinating high-risk groups over a two-and-a-half-month period in 2023. The secondary aim was to institute and track the utilization of CD testing. The MVT facilitator used the PARIHS model to guide the project, which was widely accepted by those offered testing. While successful in testing and vaccination, the team found challenges in reaching positive cases for aftercare and results. MVT will further evaluate the impact of the team, the number of patients that can be seen in high-risk groups, and the addition of a nurse practitioner to the MVT for real-time treatment and street medicine.

Keywords: Social determinants of health, COVID-19, PARIHS, vaccination, communicable disease testing.

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Background

The communicable infection, COVID-19, became a global pandemic in 2020. Over 102,000,000 cases and 1,100,000 deaths occurred in the United States (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention [CDC], 2020a). COVID-19 had a global impact with its disease burden, lockdowns, and supply shortages, but it impacted some communities disproportionately. In addition to higher hospitalization and mortality rates and lower vaccination coverage, ethnic minorities demonstrated greater vaccine reluctance (Tai et al., 2022). In late 2020, COVID-19 vaccines became available to the public to protect against hospitalization and mortality (CDC, 2020b). COVID-19 is not the only disease of concern, however. While the world struggled with managing COVID-19 through the pandemic, communicable diseases (CDs) continued to rise, and infection (STI) data showed a rise in gonorrhea and syphilis, among others (CDC, 2022b). There remained a disconnect between communities at risk for disease and the receipt of vaccination and support services due, in part, to a lack of focused efforts in the communities or an inequitable distribution of services to underserved regions, affecting those affected by inequitable social determinants of health (SDoH) (Attonito et al., 2021). COVID-19 is just one example of a communicable infection and its unbalanced impact on those in vulnerable communities. Ensuring these susceptible populations have access to the necessary resources and support to obtain vaccines and care is crucial. Groups negatively affected by SDoH have a higher prevalence of COVID-19, transmissible disease, and lower vaccination rates.

Residents of Los Angeles County (LAC) have seen disproportionate effects from COVID-19 related to SDoH and are unequally vaccinated, as those with the highest case rates had the lowest vaccine coverage (LA County Department of Public Health, 2023b). Some reasons for unequal vaccination are associated with SDoH, which are nonclinical variables that

impact the health of individuals (CDC, 2022c). In addition to the more extensive set of factors and systems that affect the atmosphere of everyday life, SDoH are the conditions that individuals are born into, grow up in, work, live in, and mature in. Racism, the environment, political institutions, and social norms are some of these factors and structures that are negative determinants of health (CDC, 2022c). Negative SDoH locations include environments where people live that adversely affect health and quality of life. Social determinants can affect various diseases, including COVID-19 (U.S. Department of Health and Human Services, 2020).

LAC's age-adjusted death rate for Black people, Latinos, and those in poverty remains elevated over white, Asian, and affluent people (LA County Department of Public Health, 2023b). Other concerns around SDoH include racism and the historic abuses of African Americans, which have led to a long-standing distrust of the government. This distrust overlapped with COVID-19 and vaccine hesitancy, where vaccine rates were low, and death rates were high (Best et al., 2021).

Problem Statement

People in groups affected by disparate SDoH have been disproportionately affected by COVID-19 and other CDs. Examples of those most affected by high rates of disease are people experiencing homelessness (PEH), those with economic disadvantage, people of certain ethnic groups, and elderly individuals. This disproportionality is observed in the California Department of Public Health (CDPH, 2023) maintained COVID-19 dashboard, which shows that over 70 percent of COVID-19 deaths occurred in those over age 65. Efforts targeting marginalized groups can decrease hospitalization and death. However, only 39 percent of those 65 and older have received booster vaccination (LA County Department of Public Health, 2023a). During the implementation of COVID-19 vaccines, inhabitants of minority communities and neighborhoods

with high disease rates received fewer immunizations and, therefore, less protection, even though Point of Dispensing sites were located throughout LAC (Dooling, 2020). Because of the unequal receipt of vaccines, certain groups had a disproportionately higher number of COVID-19 infections and fatalities while obtaining fewer immunizations than other groups.

COVID-19 is one of the concerning communicable infections affecting some communities more than others within LAC. There is an unequal impact from other communicable infections, such as STIs. The Los Angeles County Department of Public Health (LACDPH) (n.d.) reports rising case rates of syphilis, gonorrhea, and chlamydia, with even higher rates in minority communities. County mapping shows the highest STI rates in socioeconomically disadvantaged areas, racial minorities, or demographically disadvantaged (Los Angeles County Department of Public Health, 2017). Therefore, in Los Angeles, reporting shows ongoing concerns about higher CD levels in vulnerable communities.

Project Purpose

This Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) project aimed to evaluate the implementation of the mobile vaccine team (MVT) to address disparities in disease and vaccination for neighborhoods and people affected by negative SDoH. The MVT provides services directly to the communities needing them. Having an MVT was an opportunity for increased equity and direct access to a knowledgeable nursing team that could educate patients about vaccines, decrease hesitancy, and conveniently provide screening services in the area where people work and reside, thereby diminishing barriers. Formed to combat COVID-19 through vaccination, the mobile team has worked countywide, providing vaccination services, and used the California Healthy Places Index (HPI) to target the most underserved (Public Health Alliance of Southern California, n.d.). Still, other infectious diseases have continued to affect the community. For

example, STI rates continue to increase in LAC. Therefore, this project aimed to examine the effectiveness of mobile teams in adopting vaccination services in conjunction with CD screening in LAC. The following questions guided this project: In LAC residents served by mobile vaccination teams, what is the number and type of vaccines provided through mobile services? What is the utilization of STI testing and follow-up treatment services across two and a half months of implementation?

As the mobile vaccination team prioritized areas affected by adverse social determinants related to age, homelessness, and minority communities, an evaluation was done to assess vaccine and CD screening access and utilization. An effective mobile team outreach program in LAC ensures mobile team services can pivot to other diseases and needs, such as Ebola, measles, dengue, tuberculosis (TB), MPOX, STIs, and childhood vaccines.

Theoretical Framework

Theoretical frameworks are essential tools for putting evidence into practice. For many reasons, it is challenging to translate evidence into practice; therefore, it may take years for clinical practice to be current with updated evidence. Implementing scientific findings is one of the most critical responsibilities for healthcare professionals and the DNP. The challenges are numerous, and nurses cite distinct reasons for the delay in applying evidence into practice. These reasons include barriers like a lack of nurses' knowledge around the use of evidence-based practice (EBP), nurses' attitude toward EBP, as well as organizational barriers like a lack of support, supervision, and training, or limited resources, and time constraints (Alatawi et al., 2020). One implementation framework model is the Promoting Action on Research Implementation in Health Services (PARiHS). This model was designed to help implement

evidence into practice and was the most appropriate framework for this project (Rycroft-Malone, 2004).

Overview of PARIHS

The PARIHS model is different from other frameworks in that there is a strong emphasis on the importance of context and how evidence, context, and facilitation depend on each other. The practical approach of PARIHS has been successfully adapted across several care settings. This model has been used effectively for twenty-five years since its 1998 publication, and in 2016, the model was expanded to create the integrated i-PARIHS framework (Harvey & Kitson, 2016). The i-PARIHS framework expands on the original PARIHS paradigm by emphasizing individual and team behavior in implementing evidence-based procedures. This improved method focuses on healthcare delivery and patient outcomes. The framework's three key components—evidence, context, and facilitation—depend equally on where the new evidence was presented, how it was enabled, and the quality of the evidence (Rycroft-Malone, 2004).

Components of PARIHS

PARIHS has three key components: evidence, context, and facilitator. Evidence is considered the research or information that instigates the change. Evidence also includes knowledge, patient experiences, and clinical experiences (Rycroft-Malone, 2004). Second, context is the environment in which the change will occur. Context is more than a place. It also involves the available culture, leadership, and resources (Rycroft-Malone, 2004). Finally, the facilitator is responsible for implementing the change, supporting the team, and embracing the transition (Glegg & Hoens, 2016; Rycroft-Malone, 2004). Appendix A, Figures 1 and Appendix B, Figure 2 demonstrate that the components of PARIHS are interdependent and exert mutual impact.

PARiHS Projects

The PARiHS framework has been widely applied in community health settings; thus, this model aligns with the proposed project. The PARiHS technique was employed in treating diabetes in Alberta, with the premise that for knowledge translation to be effective, demonstration of benefit, a climate favorable to implementation, and facilitation to enhance acceptance were all required (Rosenthal et al., 2015). The expanded PARiHS framework was used in Australian indigenous care and was useful in analyzing system interventions (Laycock et al., 2018). The PARiHS concept was utilized in Tanzania to organize communities around the issue of postpartum deaths that could have been prevented and improve continuity of treatment (Pallangyo et al., 2017). Furthermore, the PARiHS paradigm has been implemented in community-based COVID-19 research (Frimpong et al., 2022). The framework continues to be effective in various contexts, specifically in community change settings and remains applicable to new research as facilitators can utilize it in all healthcare arenas. Thus, it was the correct framework for this DNP project.

In this project for the Department of Public Health, the facilitator was the DNP scholar, an active implementer, a nursing director, and a supervisor who knew the implementation process, how ready the agency and its staff were for change, and the environment in which the change was to be made. As a facilitator, the nursing director had access to staff to conduct change and leadership approval to drive the change and was able to conduct meetings and training in an interactive process to facilitate changes. In the PARiHS framework, a facilitator exists as a person or team who steers the group toward change as they guide others to adopt evidence into practice. A facilitator adapts their responsibilities and styles to the circumstances

and context in which they work (Harvey & Kitson, 2016; Rycroft-Malone, 2004). This facilitator role, as described in PARIHS, mirrors the role of the DNP facilitator for the project.

The project context was the LACDPH mobile vaccine team. Context is descriptive of the setting (Rycroft-Malone, 2004). This team was created for the COVID-19 response and was encouraged by leadership to meet the needs of communities affected by disparate SDoH. Leadership aligned with the need to vaccinate, test, and treat communities at the highest disease risk. The barriers to this project were implementing new electronic medical record (EMR) technology in the field and new technical skills for field testing, including phlebotomy and fingerstick. Other barriers were the staff needing technical training to conduct STI testing and training on using the EMR, acceptance of mobile testing services in the community, and staff hesitancy to adopt new working procedures in addition to the prior role of vaccination only. The benefit of adding screening services to an existing team was that the team was already providing targeted community services and had access to mobile sites with populations in LAC that had historically inadequate access to care. This additional service was seen as useful because it provided additional community support and aimed to decrease CD risk within the community.

The evidence that supported this project's initiation was shown in the evidence that historically, people have taken advantage of services when they are readily available and delivered directly to them in a convenient location (Malone et al., 2020). COVID-19 and other vaccinations have been adopted as a convenience in the workplace, pharmacy, or school when people do not need to leave to access services. Therefore, a mobile team that could provide services benefits the community by increasing care availability for those with limited access. Additionally, evidence to support this project's initiation was found in scholarly literature, which supports implementing evidence for mobile clinics into practice.

The updated PARiHS model centers on evidence, context, and the role of the facilitator in implementing new practices (Harvey & Kitson, 2016). Because the Mobile Outreach Team was evidence-based, had strong facilitation, and occurred in a setting that needed and welcomed services, PARiHS was the most appropriate framework for this project.

Review of Literature

Overview

This DNP project required a literature review since this review enabled the synthesis and analysis of all relevant literature for the project, highlighting the project's purpose and need in conjunction with current evidence (Roush, 2019). This project aimed to evaluate the impact of mobile clinic teams sent out to screen for CD and to provide vaccine services for individuals who needed services and were also subject to significant SDoH barriers. Mobile vaccination teams were a ground-breaking innovation during COVID-19, conceived to ensure equity and access to care. The team's evolution of services to include screening was an effort to continue to meet community needs where there is an observed need (Leibowitz et al., 2021). This literature review concentrated on the following topics: guidelines for mobile clinic services, immunizations/vaccines, STI testing, the prevalence of STIs, SDoH, and STIs in vulnerable groups.

Literature Search

A comprehensive search of the available literature was conducted in preparation for this project. The databases CINAHL, PubMed, and Google Scholar were searched using the following search terms: "mobile clinics," "HIV," "STI or STI," "syphilis," "vulnerable," "access," "social determinants," "PARIHS," "COVID," "immunization," "hesitancy," "vaccination," and "homeless." It was decided not to include "mobile apps," as this term led to articles unrelated to the subject. In addition to the search criteria, the journal articles contained references to relevant papers and citations used. In this search, the limitations imposed were that journal articles had to be peer-reviewed, published in 2003 or later, and written in English to be eligible for consideration. U.S. and non-U.S. literature were included. The research on mobile clinics

specific to STIs was limited in the U.S. and found more readily in rural areas and other countries. Testing and treatment guidelines from the CDC, U.S. Preventative Services Task Force, U.S. Department of Health and Human Services, and current local health department disease statistics were searched and utilized.

Social Determinants of Health

The variables that can affect an individual's health are referred to together under the umbrella phrase "social determinants of health." The environments in which people are born, where they live and reside, the places they go, and the people they are, all contribute to SDoH. The concept of SDOH encompasses various factors such as having enough money, residing in a safe location, encountering discrimination or racism, geographic location where one is born and lives, learning environment, employment, recreation, where one worships, and the aging process (U.S. Department of Health and Human Services, 2020). These factors impact the outcomes and hazards associated with health, functioning, and quality of life (U.S. Department of Health and Human Services, 2020). The COVID-19 pandemic served to shine a light on the racial and ethnic disparities and SDoH inequities within the U.S. (Hacker et al., 2022). SDoH significantly impacts people's health, well-being, and quality of life. Some examples of positive SDoH include the availability of safe housing, transportation, and communities; the absence of racism, discrimination, and violence; educational possibilities, employment prospects, and financial stability (U.S. Department of Health and Human Services, 2020). Opportunities for engaging in physically active pursuits and eating nutrient-dense meals, air and water pollution, and language and literacy problems are all SDoH. Addressing SDoH concerns is essential because people who have disparate SDoH may have a lower socioeconomic level, be immigrants, be homeless, be marginalized, be members of a minority, be vulnerable, and have a higher risk of contracting a

communicable illness as well as a reduced capacity to get medical treatment (Caton et al., 2012; CDC, 2021; Chesson et al., 2017; Hacker et al., 2022; Tabler et al., 2018; U.S. Department of Health and Human Services, 2020; Valentine et al., 2022).

Sexually Transmitted Infections

It is reported that in the United States, one in five people has an STI, and in 2018, chlamydia was the most prevalent reportable STI, accounting for over 1,800,000 cases (CDC, 2022a; Valentine et al., 2022). STIs are expensive in the US, both financially and in terms of long-term health consequences. Furthermore, specific populations are disproportionately affected by STIs and face a greater risk of infection than others. This disproportionate impact causes morbidity and mortality in women and children (Chesson et al., 2017). STIs also place a significant global financial and health burden on society, and where sociocultural, economic, and political contexts also influence sexual behavior (Chesson et al., 2017). Although the U.S. Preventative Services Task Force (n.d.) recommends that people at risk for STIs be tested and treated, the disease burden is still present and increasing. STI rates continue to rise both nationally and locally. Increased sexual risk and STIs are linked to homelessness and unstable housing situations (Caton et al., 2012; Jenness et al., 2011; Marshall et al., 2009). The burden of STI infections is higher in those communities, whether they are women, people of color, men who have sex with men, sex workers, or anyone others impacted by inequities of SDoH (Caton et al., 2012; CDC, 2021) To lessen the burden of STIs, targeted interventions are required (Caton et al., 2012; Chesson et al., 2017; Tabler et al., 2018; Valentine et al., 2022). These interventions should be made considering each group's unique needs. Research has suggested that targeted interventions, such as education and mobile services, are methods that can improve and address

SDoH inequities (Alfieri et al., 2021; Balut et al., 2022; Gatwood et al., 2021; Thomas et al., 2018; Wheeler et al., 2021; Wyte-Lake et al., 2022).

Vaccination

Vaccines have been widely regarded as one of the most effective disease-preventive strategies for public health in the last century; nonetheless, many individuals are concerned about their safety and efficacy (Siddiqui et al., 2013). Hesitancy has been a barrier to vaccination for numerous reasons, but one fundamental cause is a lack of trust in the government, providers, or vaccines themselves. There is a lack of confidence when people need more knowledge or are given incorrect information. For vulnerable communities, trust and access concerns related to vaccines have been exacerbated by historical racial imbalances (Dada et al., 2022). There is evidence, however, that the provision of mobile vaccines in needy communities can ensure care goes to those who would not have received it otherwise by using a trusted community location with convenient access (Van Alphen et al., 2023).

Many studies to examine attitudes and behaviors surrounding COVID-19 immunization revealed increased hesitancy in Black Americans and minority groups, as well as the necessity for tailored interventions (Alfieri et al., 2021; Gatwood et al., 2021). Vaccine acceptance has been proven to increase with access, education, and trustworthy connections (Balut et al., 2022; Wyte-Lake et al., 2022). Mobile health clinics are community-based venues that provide direct access and are extensively used to expand access for high-risk, socially disadvantaged, or minority patients in high-minority areas to increase equity (Malone et al., 2020).

Mobile Clinics

Mobile services can act as a resource for the community because they provide healthcare to disadvantaged populations and make it possible for those who would not otherwise have

access to healthcare to obtain it in clinical settings (Grieb et al., 2022; Malone et al., 2020; Rousseau et al., 2021; Stallmach et al., 2023). Young individuals, persons who engage in transactional sexual activity, people from rural regions, people from underrepresented groups, and drug injectors are all more likely to utilize mobile services (Grieb et al., 2022; Malone et al., 2020; Rousseau et al., 2021; Stallmach et al., 2023). Several studies suggest that mobile health clinics improve access to healthcare in underserved communities because the providers travel directly to the community to provide locally available care and rapid access in an environment that is typically cost-free and easily accessible (Malone et al., 2020). When a mobile clinic is available, the barrier of making an appointment or traveling is removed. Mobile health clinics provide care in an environment that is easily accessible, often does not cost anything to the recipient, and eliminates barriers such as transportation (Bouchelle et al., 2017; Grieb et al., 2022; Malone et al., 2020; Rousseau et al., 2021; Stallmach et al., 2023).

Furthermore, Mobile clinics are linked to elevated levels of patient satisfaction because clients like the convenient times and locations, low levels of stigma and judgment when receiving care, compassionate staff, increased speed of service, and the ability to go in conveniently and stress-free without an appointment. Staff members at these specialized services are well-versed in the local community and speak understandably to members of the broader public (Bouchelle et al., 2017; Grieb et al., 2022; Rousseau et al., 2021; Stallmach et al., 2023). Mobile clinics are linked to elevated levels of patient satisfaction because clients like the convenient times and locations, low levels of stigma and judgment when receiving care, compassionate staff, increased speed of service, and the ability to go in conveniently and stress-free without an appointment. Staff members at these specialized services are well-versed in the

local community and speak understandably to members of the broader public (Bouchelle et al., 2017; Grieb et al., 2022; Rousseau et al., 2021; Stallmach et al., 2023).

PARiHS Framework

A literature review through PUBMED and Google Scholar revealed numerous projects that use the PARiHS framework. The PARiHS framework is a valuable resource for assessing the application of evidence-based practices in healthcare settings. This model considers the interaction of evidence, context, and facilitation to evaluate the efficacy of implementation efforts (Rycroft-Malone, 2004). Since its inception in the 1990s, this framework has guided applying evidence to practice in various contexts. Musanti et al. (2012) used the PARiHS model to implement a new change in the nursing practice model. The aim of this DNP project was like Musanti et al. (2012) in that it examined the leadership team's facilitation, the context of their health system, evidence from qualitative and quantitative data, and a review of recent findings in the literature. This DNP project aimed to use the DNP student as a facilitator in public healthcare using the contextual and academic evidence discovered through the research. PARiHS includes dynamic roles in which recent evidence and contextual support interact. One government project that uses the PARiHS framework, the Veterans Health Administration (VHA), suggested a guideline to improve care coordination for those with hepatitis C (Rongey et al., 2011). The PARiHS framework was proposed because of its interconnected elements, which indicate that successful implementation is supported when the evidence is sound, the healthcare context is open to implementation with its leadership and culture, and mechanisms to facilitate implementation are present (Rongey et al., 2011). According to Rongey et al. (2011), the intervention should be tailored to the context by using data collected locally and through research

on the vulnerable population as evidence. The facilitator should ensure that the evidence is implemented within the context.

Summary

In summary, SDoH can positively or negatively affect disease outcomes (U.S. Department of Health and Human Services, 2020). STIs remain high in LAC, nationally and worldwide, with those having high-risk SDoH indicators disproportionately affected at higher rates (Los Angeles County Department of Public Health, 2017). Mobile clinics are effective and precisely positioned to meet the community where they are and provide services. These mobile clinics are most utilized by ethnic minorities and vulnerable populations (Malone et al., 2020). The mobile clinic team used U.S. Preventative Task Force (n.d.) recommendations to provide screening and meet this unmet need for screening and vaccinating.

For this DNP project, guided by the PARiHS framework, the DNP facilitator evaluated the implementation of CD and STI testing for underserved communities using the mobile health clinic model that was used previously to administer vaccinations solely. As the pandemic prompted this LAC team to serve its community and promote equity, the mobile clinic model was used for proactive outreach to community members. This model has been used globally and can be a trusted community resource that reduces access barriers, such as mistrust among historically underserved and marginalized communities (Mayfield et al., 2023). Daily, teams traveled throughout LAC to provide services in various contexts, such as homeless encampments, Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, Transgender, Queer (LGBTQ) Pride events, workplaces, and outreach events. The team added testing for those at risk for CDs such as HIV, syphilis, gonorrhea, and chlamydia, following the U.S. Preventative Task Force's (n.d.) recommendations to combat rising STI rates in the county and disproportionate population impacts. This care

model is adaptable to current needs and is responsive to data-informed decision-making strategies for delivering targeted services. It is part of a larger strategy to establish diverse entry points into the healthcare system at the most convenient time for community members.

Methods

The methods section is an essential piece of the doctoral project. This section describes the methodology and instruments used to create a doctoral project and informs the validity thereof (Roush, 2019). This DNP project aimed to evaluate the impact of using mobile clinic teams initially deployed to provide vaccination services as teams that screen for communicable infections at designated sites and provide vaccination services to individuals. These services were given in communities within LAC, targeted primarily to those at risk for communicable infection and locations where recipients were subject to significant disparate SDoH using HPI mapping (Public Health Alliance of Southern California, n.d.).

Design

The design of this project was a quality improvement (QI) with an evaluation of metrics. For this project to succeed in meeting its objectives, a strategy centered on quality enhancement was implemented with a program evaluation of evidence-driven QI. The PARIHS framework was used as a guide for reviewing clinical practice guidelines and other evidence for this project. Nurses used these guidelines and a testing protocol to provide STI and CD screening to patients who present themselves for service at mobile vaccine clinics in LAC. Context, evidence, and facilitation are the three components of the PARIHS model used together to put evidence into practice and evaluate the project.

Ethical Considerations

Before beginning the project, approval was obtained from the LACDPH Institutional Review Board (IRB), LACDPH clinical management, and the IRB at California State University, Los Angeles. A letter from the LACDPH Clinical Director granting permission to conduct the project at the agency was requested and received. During this project, information technology

specialists collected deidentified data and metrics and gave this information to the DNP student. During the process of data extraction for the project, no personally identifiable patient information was gathered. The documented results were kept on a spreadsheet housed on a secured computer in the locked office of the primary author. The lead author is the only person who had access to the computer because it is password-protected and was kept in a locked desk within a locked room.

Institutional review board (IRB) approval from California State University, Los Angeles, was secured before the project commenced. All approvals are shown in Appendix C.

Sample and Setting

This project focused on a sample of patients who visited mobile vaccine and testing clinics operating within various locations across LAC. The clinical settings for the project were the sites served by mobile outreach clinic teams throughout LAC. The clinics were part of a mobile outreach initiative staffed by a team of over one hundred individuals, including nurses, community workers, and administrative staff. These teams provided consistent vaccination and testing services for communicable and STIs across the county daily. While the specific locations varied daily, services such as vaccinations or screening tests were offered at sites like places of worship, workplaces, homeless shelters, Pride events, and residences of homebound patients.

Procedure

Sites were designated as vaccination sites or vaccination and testing sites. At vaccination-only sites, patients arriving for services were assessed for current vaccination status and vaccine needs. Patients were also assessed for CD screening needs at sites that included screening. At locations with screening, patients were made aware that CD screening was available through flyers, community worker outreach, or at the time of registration. When scheduling with the site

point of contact (POC), the practice standard was to offer services for CD screening along with immunization and share flyers with information about mobile services. On the day of the event, verbal onsite screening offers were made as patients sought mobile services. During the initial intake, if the patient appeared too ill or had signs and symptoms beyond the scope of a mobile clinic, they were referred to emergency care services or the nearest LACDPH Clinic, as appropriate.

The vaccinations prioritized for use by the mobile vaccination team were those for COVID-19, influenza, and MPOX. Additional vaccination types were provided, including school entry vaccinations provided through the Vaccines for Children (VFC) program and Hepatitis A vaccines, given due to local outbreaks. The mobile team provided VFC vaccines in school settings and outreach events and to unaccompanied migrants as requested. High-risk locations were utilized for mobile testing, including migrant sites, homeless settings, and Pride events. Staff received training in the EMR and communicable infection testing. They provided testing for HIV and Syphilis using rapid fingerstick tests. Phlebotomy tests were given for HIV, syphilis, and TB. Self-collected urine, throat, and rectal swabs for gonorrhea and chlamydia were initiated. Specimens went to diagnostic laboratories for processing. All send-out results were received, tracked, and followed by the telehealth team; patients with positive results were referred to the clinic for follow-up. The team provided the project lead with deidentified, aggregated data about services completed, including types of sites, number of tests, number of treated patients, other services provided, and patients lost to follow-up.

Measures and Evaluation

This project aimed to evaluate the impact of mobile vaccines and STI screening in mobile care. De-identified metrics, including the numbers of testing sites, people evaluated, those who

tested positive, number treated, and vaccinated, were provided, and analyzed. Data were analyzed using Excel and the Statistical Package for the Social Science (SPSS). Descriptive statistics, and the results were used to identify trends and patterns and inform future interventions. Additionally, the deidentified data collected protected the privacy of mobile service users.

Conclusion

The method section provides an overview of the QI project, covering its design, relevant ethical issues, processes, sample, and evaluation measures. This section, a vital component of the doctoral project, provides insight into the project's validity (Roush, 2019). Additionally, it clarifies each of the steps that were taken to ensure the project's success.

Results

The results section in this DNP project presents the findings clearly and succinctly. This section includes reports of the data collected without interpreting the findings. The results form a foundation for discussion and implications. The results are based upon the time used for this project, between July 26, 2023, through October 13, 2023. Evaluation of metrics was completed, including numbers of vaccinations, screening tests, locations served, and services provided, including follow-up and attempted treatment initiation.

Data Analysis

Excel documents were received from the LACDPH data team. Data was deidentified before receipt to remove any patient information and identifiers. Data included sites, type of sites (PEH, migrant, Pride), treatments, vaccines, results disclosure, an offer of portal access, referrals for follow-up in-person care, telehealth services, in-person education, in-person harm reduction, receipt of patient contact information, education provided, interest in HIV prevention (PrEP) and clearances provided. The date range was July 26, 2023, through October 13, 2023. Vaccine data was also provided for comparison from July 26, 2022, through October 13, 2022. Data was reviewed in Excel and Power BI. Data was taken from Excel format and transferred into SPSS version 28 for additional analysis. Data was analyzed, viewed, and reviewed in these three systems.

Vaccines

During the evaluation period, 6,048 vaccinations were provided by the MVT across all sites. The most common vaccines provided were COVID-19, Flu, MPOX, and Hepatitis A. Of note, pediatric vaccines were a newly offered service. Over 380 pediatric vaccines were provided for those aged 18 and under at back-to-school and other community events (Appendix D, Table

1). There was a total of 508 mobile sites during this period, and of those events, 43 sites provided both testing and vaccines. Of the 6,048 vaccines provided, 492 doses were given at sites that offered testing and vaccines. The MVT provided eleven types of vaccines. These included COVID-19 (2,849), Flu (1,958), Mpox (642), Hepatitis A (216), and the pediatric vaccines DTaP (4), Hepatitis B (63), HPV (9), MMR (65), Polio (68), Tdap (109), and Varicella (65).

The percentage of sites that offered screening tests was 8.5%, and the number of vaccines provided at the combined sites was also 8.1% of the total vaccines during that period (Appendix D, Table 2). During the same period one year prior, the team administered 14,464 doses across 583 sites. Those sites did not offer any testing. The vaccines provided at that time were MPOX (8,409), COVID-19 (6,043), and Flu (12) (Appendix D, Table 3).

Communicable Disease Testing

Across the 43 screening sites, 179 patients received testing. The most common site type was PEH, which had 40 locations. In addition, there were two migrant sites and 1 Pride event. Of the 179 individuals tested, 163 were PEH, eight were at a Pride event, and eight were from migrant locations. Over 91% of those tested were PEH (Appendix D, Table 4).

Testing was provided through rapid fingerstick tests or send-out labs. Of the 179 patients who received any test, there was 1 (.6%) positive rapid syphilis test and zero positive rapid HIV tests, giving a .6% positivity rate for rapid tests (Appendix D, Tables 5 and 6). Patients opted in or out to receive rapid tests for HIV and syphilis and send-out tests that included confirmatory syphilis, confirmatory HIV, gonorrhea (GC), chlamydia (CT), and T-SPOT. The most ordered test was T-SPOT, with 130 tests. Other tests were HIV (56), syphilis (57), and GC-CT, with 57 tests (Appendix D, Table 7).

GC and CT testing included the anatomical sites of vaginal, rectal, pharyngeal, and urine. Urine was the most common testing method for GC-CT (Appendix D, Table 8). Eighteen patients had positive send-out labs, and three patients had invalid or borderline results, requiring nursing staff to notify them that a follow-up test was needed. The positive send-out rate from the 179 tested was 10.2% (Appendix D, Table 9). The combination of positive rapid tests at .6% with the send-out results yielded a positive rate of 10.8%. A patient portal and telehealth combination were used to provide patient test results. Over 63% of those tested accepted the patient portal to access results. However, only 21.8% activated the portal, requiring an attempted secondary method of contact (Appendix D, Tables 10 and 11).

Three patients (1.7%) provided no phone number or contact information (Appendix D, Table 12). Fifty-four (30.2%) patients could not be contacted through provided information to disclose results (Appendix D, Table 13). However, 110 (61.41%) patients had results disclosed by phone, through EMR messaging, or via an authorized shelter manager. Fifteen (8.4%) did not require any follow-up disclosure due to rapid testing without send-out labs. Three (1.7%) patients with positive STI results were referred to the STI division, and seven (3.9%) were referred to the TB Control program after being unable to locate treatment. There was one positive chlamydia positive individual who was booked into the clinic for STI follow-up. One person was booked into the TB clinic for a chest X-ray follow-up (Appendix D, Table 14). Medical clearance was provided to 108 individuals (Appendix D, Table 15).

At testing sites, over 96% of patients received ancillary services consisting of STI and substance abuse harm reduction strategies including verbal and written education as appropriate (Appendix D, Table 16). Education related to STI and HIV, included consultation regarding the need for PrEP and PEP. Additional ancillary services consisted of consultation, distribution of

medication, or medical supplies. For those at risk of opiate overdose, education regarding the administration of Narcan and the use of Fentanyl test strips was provided. Risk reduction supplies were provided to patients. In all, 104 units of Narcan and 135 Fentanyl test strips were dispensed and accepted at PEH events (Appendix D, Table 17).

Discussion

The discussion section presents the key findings, implications, and recommendations. In this DNP project, the author sought to implement screening tests at mobile sites in designated high-risk locations previously used throughout the community for COVID-19 vaccines. The author facilitator used the PARIHS framework to guide the integration of the new practice into existing practice. Data was collected and integrated through Excel, Power BI, and SPSS charts and graphs. The EMR and data collection system Microsoft Customer Relationship Management were used as sources of information. The facilitator continued to have daily briefings with the team throughout the time to coordinate efforts and ensure engagement. The daily meetings allowed for real-time feedback and correction within the context as evidence was put into practice.

Communicable diseases continue to impact lives with high rates of infection, loss of life, and loss of time away from work. The impact of CD on those disproportionately affected by SDoH remains challenging, but research has demonstrated that methods to target inequities can be effective in improving care and decreasing inequities (Alfieri et al., 2021; Balut et al., 2022; Gatwood et al., 2021; Thomas et al., 2018; Wheeler et al., 2021; Wyte-Lake et al., 2022). Not only do interventions for those affected by CDs combat inequities, these interventions for testing and vaccinations are cost-effective as they reduce hospitalization, disease complications, healthcare burden, and deaths (Chesson et al., 2021; Eckman et al., 2021; Padula et al., 2021; Shrestha et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2021).

More widely, the identification of CD provided an opportunity for treatment and mitigation of the spread of disease. Disease-lessening strategies such as vaccinations, as well as testing and treating CD, limit the disease rate and spread of disease in the community, thereby

reducing disease impact and case burden (Brüningk et al., 2022). Directing services to where patients are remains a significant factor in accepting clinical interventions (Leibowitz et al., 2021). Although the number of patients tested and treated was not statistically significant, it was clinically significant in that each patient tested and treated or with knowledge of their disease status, and each patient educated on health safety is a person reached to lower the local burden and spread of CDs.

This project highlights the effective strategies implemented for delivering vaccinations and testing through mobile units and the insights gained from these efforts. Addressing negative SDoH, specifically access to health care and financial constraints, significantly increased vaccinations and STI testing. Access to at-risk populations also allowed for providing additional services, such as Narcan and other harm-reduction supplies.

Key Findings: Vaccination

MVT provided access to vaccines by bringing them to locations with little access, meeting the SDoH concern. Vaccination is a life-saving preventative healthcare measure and one of the most effective public health measures of the last 100 years (Siddiqui et al., 2013). By the end of March 2024, MVT has provided over 156,000 doses (Appendix D, Table 18). From July 26, 2023, to October 13, 2023, nurses and community workers attended mobile events, providing vaccines at 508 sites, including 43 sites that provided combined services of vaccination and testing. Comparing services to the same date range one year prior provides additional information. There were no pediatric sites in 2022; however, by 2023, the team had added this service and provided 383 pediatric back-to-school vaccinations. The total number of vaccinations provided in 2022 was higher at 14,464 primarily related to COVID-19 (6043) and MPOX (8,409) vaccination counts. This is in part related to the county response to an international

MPOX outbreak which increased MPOX vaccination (Laurenson-Schafer et al., 2023).

Additionally, 2022 was earlier in the COVID-19 pandemic; thus, there was increased vaccination uptake of COVID-19 vaccine. However, the number of flu vaccines increased in 2023 (1,958) along with all childhood vaccinations.

Key Findings: Testing

As the team added testing, there was no decrease in vaccination at collocated sites that featured both vaccination and testing. MVT sites with concurrent testing and vaccination made up 8.1% of vaccinations and 8.4% of vaccine sites, adding 179 patients who received screening. Most testing locations served primarily PEH. PEH individuals experience high rates of concerning CD, are often immune compromised, and are susceptible to CDs. Thus, testing in shelters is highly encouraged (Tibbetts et al., 2020). Lost to follow-up was a finding in 30% of patients, meaning those patients did not have a method to be contacted, did not activate their patient communication portal after accepting it, or may not have had internet access. Lost to follow-up is a common finding in PEH population as is the high rate of non-adherence to prescribed treatment (Lopez et al., 2022). Although follow-up was difficult, testing was widely accepted, as were harm reduction supplies. Had the MVT not been present in the area for the patients, they would not have received testing, vaccination, education, or harm reduction.

Recommendations and Implications

This project should be sustained and supported as it meets the needs of those with inadequate access to care. However, improvements should be made. Point-of-care treatment for symptomatic patients at the time of testing would allow PEH patients to be treated and eliminate many concerns around loss of follow-up or inability to obtain medication; treatment that could be completed with one-time medication administered at the mobile clinic would address non-

adherence issues (Lopez et al., 2022). Nyamathi et al., 2023 demonstrated that street medicine increased medication adherence and showed that treating PEH with Hepatitis C was effective when delivered directly. As treatment and follow-up of positive patients were most concerning and patients had to be referred interdepartmentally after loss to treatment, it is recommended that MVT have a provider on hand for real-time care and treatment.

The MVT may consider partnering with those in social work, the Department of Mental Health, or social work educational internships, as mental health services are needed for at-risk populations and are effective in a street medicine model (Su et al., 2024). The MVT should also consider a full menu of testing services, including Hepatitis B and C, Trichomonas, and pregnancy, to increase access and referrals.

The MVT started as a pilot team to ensure vaccination for the most underserved. The team is now a permanent program within the clinical branch of LACDPH. The MVT has been successful in vaccinating and reaching the neediest. This QI project was used to examine vaccination and testing efforts. The team should continue this work to prevent future infections and be responsive during outbreaks. Increased effectiveness can be achieved by continuing to provide vaccines, expanding testing services, and adding a nurse practitioner to provide point-of-service treatment. Local and federal grants may fund the expansion of these services.

Limitations

There were certain limitations to this project. The limitations include the period for data collection, which included just 2.5 months of vaccination, testing, and follow-up information. These findings are limited to LAC and not generalizable to other locations; however, this project may be replicated in other cities. Testing sites were limited in that the point of contact for the location needed to approve a testing team to come, and space for a vehicle and privacy were site

requirements. Other limitations were the lack of a provider and the necessity to make a referral for any services needed.

Conclusions

Although vaccinations and testing sites can be found throughout the LAC, many areas are underserved. MVT represents an opportunity to provide care where it is most needed. Based on the results of this QI project, it is recommended that the MVT continue to provide vaccination and screening and expand the program further by adding a mid-level provider.

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Appendix A

Figure 1: Components of PARiHS

Note. Figure 1 is adapted from (Slaughter et al., 2013).

Appendix B

Figure 2: PARiHS Framework

Appendix C

Exemption Approval Letters

Exemption Letter California State University, Los Angeles

Office Memorandum

DATE:	July 26, 2023
TO:	Elizabeth Winokur, PhD
FROM:	Claire Riner
PROJECT TITLE:	[2060460-1] MOBILE TEAMS – REACHING HIGH-RISK COMMUNITIES WITH VACCINATION AND TESTING
REFERENCE #:	22-215X
SUBMISSION TYPE:	New Project
ACTION:	DETERMINATION OF EXEMPT STATUS
DECISION DATE:	July 26, 2023
REVIEW CATEGORY:	Exemption category # 4(ii)

Thank you for your submission of New Project materials for this project. The California State University, Los Angeles (Cal State LA) IRB has determined that this project is EXEMPT FROM IRB REVIEW according to federal regulations.

We will retain a copy of this correspondence within our records.

IF ANY CHANGES ARE MADE TO THE METHODS AND PROCEDURES DESCRIBED IN THIS PROTOCOL, YOU MUST SUBMIT A MODIFICATION APPLICATION SO THAT THE PROJECT MAY BE RE-EVALUATED FOR EXEMPTION FROM IRB REVIEW.

For any inquiries about this project, please use the Send Project Mail option on IRBNet to contact Claire Riner. **It allows us to keep all correspondence related to this project in one place, rather than scattered between IRBNet and emails.**

This letter has been electronically signed in accordance with all applicable regulations, and a copy is retained within California State University, Los Angeles (Cal State LA) IRB's records.

Department Approval Los Angeles Department of Public Health

BARBARA FERRER, Ph.D., M.P.H., M.Ed.
Director

MUNTU DAVIS, M.D., M.P.H.
County Health Officer

MEGAN McCLAIRE, M.S.P.H.
Chief Deputy Director

RITA SINGHAL, M.D., M.P.H.
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GEMA MORALES-MEYER, D.N.P., M.P.H., R.N., C.N.S.
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May 4, 2023

This letter is to show that, I, Gema Morales-Meyer, as the Director of Clinic Services for the Los Angeles County Department of Public Health, give permission to Christa Davison to conduct the project titled Mobile Teams – Reaching High-Risk Communities with Vaccination and Testing in the Mobile Outreach Teams that provide mobile clinic services.

As a quality improvement project and with approval from the Director of Clinic Services, this project is exempt from obtaining IRB approval and the above-named project lead is allowed to:

- (1) collect de-identified aggregate data
- (2) access necessary documents/data
- (3) conduct necessary interactions with staff/patients relevant to their project

The project lead is responsible for ensuring that all activities related to conducting the project are in compliance with the policies that govern practice, HIPPA, research and quality improvement regulations/guidelines at the Los Angeles County Department of Public Health- Clinic Services and its covered entities.

If you have any questions or concerns, please do not hesitate to contact me.

Sincerely,

Gema Morales-Meyer, Director of Clinic Services
Los Angeles Department of Public Health

IRB Approval Los Angeles County Department of Public Health

BARBARA FERRER, Ph.D., M.P.H., M.Ed.
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May 17, 2023

IRB Project No. 2023-05-006

TO: Christa Davison - Principal Investigator

FROM: Paul Camarena, MPH
Analyst, Los Angeles County Department of Public Health Institutional Review Board

Project title: Mobile Teams – Reaching High-Risk Communities with Vaccination and Testing

Action taken: Determination of Not Human Subjects Research, no IRB review needed
Action taken by: Analyst
Action date: May 17, 2023

As Analyst of the Los Angeles County Department of Public Health Institutional Review Board (IRB), I have reviewed your submission of the above-referenced study.

The study will collect deidentified aggregate data on the number and types of vaccination sites and tests available at those sites in order to assess whether to add STD services to Mobile Vaccine Teams.

I have determined that this study meets the criteria for not human subjects research per 45 CFR 46.102(e). Thus, IRB review is not needed. This determination applies only to the activities described to the IRB on May 17, 2023 and does not apply should any changes be made. If changes are being considered and there are questions, you must contact the IRB as soon as possible. Changes may not be implemented without the review and final approval by this IRB.

Appendix D
Results Tables

Table 1

LACDPH Mobile Team Doses Administered 7/26/23 - 10/13/23.

Vaccine Type	Sum of Doses Administered
COVID-19	2849
DTaP (Pediatric)	4
Flu	1958
Hep A	216
Hep B (Pediatric)	63
HPV (Pediatric)	9
JYNNEOS (MPox Vax)	642
MMR (Pediatric)	65
Polio IPV (Pediatric)	68
Tdap (Pediatric)	109
Varicella (Pediatric)	65
Grand Total	6048

Table 2*LACDPH Mobile Team Site Types 7/26/23 - 10/13/23*

Site Types	Site Count	Site Percent	Dose Count	Dose Percent
Vaccine	465	91.5	5556	91.9
Vaccine and Testing	43	8.3	492	8.1
Total	508	100	6048	100

Table 3

LACDPH Mobile Team Doses Administered 7/26/22 - 10/13/22.

Vaccine Type	Sum of Doses Administered
COVID-19	6043
Flu	12
JYNNEOS (MPox Vax)	8409
Grand Total	14464

Note. MPox outbreak response 2022 increased MPox vaccination

Table 4*LACDPH Mobile Team Testing Site Types 7/26/23 - 10/13/23*

	N	%
Migrant	8	4.5%
PEH	163	91.1%
Pride 2023	8	4.5%
Total	179	

Table 5*Rapid Syphilis 7/26/23 - 10/13/23*

	N	%
Negative	13	7.3%
Positive	1	0.6%
Not Applicable	165	92.2%
Total	179	

Note. The not applicable designation was for any patient who received testing other than rapid syphilis.

Table 6*Rapid HIV 7/26/23 - 10/13/23*

	N	%
Negative	17	9.5%
Not Applicable	162	90.5%
Total	179	100%

Note. The not applicable designation was for any patient who received testing other than rapid

HIV.

Table 7*Laboratory Send-Out tests 7/26/23 - 10/13/23*

	N	%
None	15	8.4%
HIV and Syphilis	5	2.8%
GC-CT and Syphilis	3	1.7%
HIV	4	2.2%
T-SPOT	91	50.8%
GC-CT	12	6.7%
GC-CT, HIV, Syphilis, and T-SPOT	30	16.8%
GC-CT, HIV, and Syphilis	10	5.6%
HIV, Syphilis, and T-SPOT	7	3.9%
GC-CT, Syphilis, and T-SPOT	2	1.1%
Total	179	100%

Note. The designation of none was used for any patient who received rapid and not send-out tests.

Table 8*Anatomical sites GC-CT 7/26/23 - 10/13/23*

	N	%
None	122	68.2%
Urine	25	14.0%
Rectal and Urine	1	0.6%
Pharyngeal and Rectal	1	0.6%
Pharyngeal	10	5.6%
Vaginal	4	2.2%
Pharyngeal, Rectal, and Urine	1	0.6%
Pharyngeal, Rectal, and Vaginal	3	1.7%
Pharyngeal and Urine	9	5.0%
Pharyngeal and Vaginal	2	1.1%
Pharyngeal, Vaginal, and Urine	1	0.6%
Total	179	100%

Note. None designation was for any patient who opted out of the GC-CT test.

Table 9*Positive Laboratory Send-Out tests 7/26/23 - 10/13/23*

	N	%
None	159	88.8%
Positive T-SPOT	6	3.4%
Invalid T-SPOT	2	1.1%
Borderline T-SPOT	1	0.6%
Positive Syphilis	8	4.5%
Positive Chlamydia	2	111%
Positive T-SPOT and HIV	1	0.6%

Note. None designation was for any patient who received rapid and not send out tests.

Table 10*Portal Access Offered for Results 7/26/23 - 10/13/23*

	N	%
No	61	34.1%
Yes	114	63.7%
N/A	4	2.2%
Total	179	

Table 11
Patient Activated Portal for Lab Results 7/26/23 - 10/13/23

	N	%
No	84	46.9%
Yes	39	21.8%
N/A	56	31.3%
Total	179	

Table 12*Phone number provided for disclosures 7/26/23 - 10/13/23*

	N	%
No	3	1.7%
Yes	167	93.3%
N/A	9	5.0%
Total	179	

Table 13
Lab Result Disclosure 7/26/23 - 10/13/23

	N	%
No	54	30.2%
Yes	82	45.8%
N/A	15	8.4%
EMR Portal Messaging	14	7.8%
Results to Predesignated Shelter Manager	14	7.8%
Total	179	

Note. N/A was for those who did not require disclosure.

Table 14*Referrals provided 7/26/23 - 10/13/23*

	Frequency	Percentage
None	167	93.2%
Sexual Health Clinic	1	0.6%
STD Division	3	1.7%
TB Chest Xray Clinic	1	0.6%
TB Control Division	7	3.9%
Total	179	

Table 15
TSPOT Clearance Provided 7/26/23 - 10/13/23

	N	Percentage
No	23	12.8%
Yes	108	60.3%
N/A	48	26.8%
Total	179	

Table 16
Educational resources 7/26/23 - 10/13/23

	N	Percentage
Yes	173	96.6%
N/A	6	3.4%
Total	179	

Table 17
Harm Reduction 7/26/23 - 10/13/23

Site Type by Month	Narcan Units Distributed	Fentanyl Strips Distributed
July	0	0
August	44	90
September	36	30
October	24	15
Total	104	135

Table 18*Mobile Team Vaccine 3/2021 - 3/2024*

Vaccine Type	Sum of Doses Administered
COVID-19	124,028
DTaP (Pediatric)	4
Flu	19,688
Hep A	425
Hep B (Pediatric)	69
HPV (Pediatric)	9
JYNNEOS (MPox Vax)	11,731
MMR (Pediatric)	77
Polio IPV (Pediatric)	80
Tdap (Pediatric)	130
Varicella (Pediatric)	74
MCV4	6
Total	156,330